

Plant origin quercetin in combating arsenic induced hepato-cellular damage in rat

M. Shivashankar^a, Anusua Das^a, Badal Kumar Mandal^{b*} and Nirmalendu Das^c

^aPharmaceutical Chemistry Division, ^bEnvironmental and Analytical Chemistry Division,
School of Advanced Sciences, VIT University, Vellore-632 014, Tamilnadu, India

E-mail : badalmandal@vit.ac.in Fax : 91-416-2243092

^cBio Membrane Division, Indian Institute of Chemical Biology, Kolkata-700 032, India

Manuscript received 25 July 2011, revised 13 January 2012, accepted 17 January 2012

Abstract : Since there is no medicine for combating arsenic induced liver fibrosis, quercetin (QC), a plant origin drug, was used to combat oxidative stress caused by arsenic to hepatic tissues of rat. Concentrations of lipohydroperoxide, superoxide dismutase (SOD) and catalases were monitored with respect to free QC and liposome intercalated QC. Liposome intercalated drugs increased antioxidant capacity as well as decreased the value of 4-hydroxy proline (4-PC) compared to the arsenite treated group. So, liposome intercalated drug showed more optimized action to liver than free drugs and quercetin is promising to combat arsenic induced hepatomegaly in the arsenic endemic areas.

Keywords : Arsenic, liver fibrosis, hepatomegaly, quercetin, liposome intercalated drug.

Introduction

Chronic arsenicosis leads to irreversible damage in several vital organs and arsenic (As) is an established carcinogen¹. Despite the magnitude of this potentially fatal toxicity, there is no effective therapy for this disease. The need for an effective therapy for chronic arsenicosis is obvious. Chelation therapy is presumed to be more effective with early features of the toxicity, as severe manifestation of polyneuropathy, chronic lung and liver disease, swelling of hand and legs, defect in hearing and vision are less likely to respond to this therapy.

Another aspect of arsenic toxicity is that it can produce or promote the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) in the target organs/cells in laboratory animals or in cultured animal and human cells, which leads to hepatotoxicity and other related diseases²⁻⁷. Inorganic arsenic increases the rate of formation of ROS including superoxide anion radical ($O_2^{\cdot-}$) and hydroxyl radical ($\cdot OH$) through a chain reaction after metabolism of inorganic arsenite into methylated arsenicals in the body⁶. Quercetin interferes with ROS metabolism and causing subsequent (QC) apoptosis. Quercetin strongly increases inter-cellular ROS level as quercetin radicals (QU-O^{*}) can be formed after peroxidase canalized oxidation in order to

scavenge reactive peroxy radicals. Quercetin can alter ROS metabolism by directly lowering the intracellular pool of GSH. Long time exposure to quercetin resulted in a decrease in cell GSH content, suggesting that an inability of quercetin cope with ROS for a long period by reacting with ROS. Quercetin conform potentially toxic oxidation production. Mandal *et al.*^{8,9} showed hepatoprotective activity of liposomal polyphenolic flavonoid against arsenite induced liver fibrosis. Plant origin polyphenolic flavonoid quercetin and its derivatives, the citrus bioflavonoid, including quercitrin, rutin and hesperidin; have also been fairly well studied⁸⁻¹³.

Quercetin is the drug of choice as it is the most abundant flavonoid in the nature, present in large amounts in vegetable, fruits, tea and olive oil, containing a number of phenolic hydroxyl groups (three in number) that exhibits its antioxidant property and therapeutic potential against many diseases, including ischemic heart diseases, atherosclerosis and liver injury in chronically biliary obstruction. Bors *et al.*¹⁰ has proposed that 3 structural groups in flavonoids are important determinants for their radical scavenging property. These are (i) *ortho*-dihydroxyl (catechol structure in the B ring) – the target site for all flavonoids; (ii) 2,3 double bond in conjugation with 4-

oxo function, which is responsible for electron delocalisation and (iii) the additional presence of two more hydroxyl groups for maximal radical scavenging potential and strongest radical absorption.

The mechanism of action of flavonoids was inferred from the oxidation of QC by lauryl peroxide radical. Both metal chelating and free radical scavenging activity of flavonoids have been accepted in biological system.

The main objectives of the present study were (i) attempt was made in the present study to check exogenous antioxidant therapy against arsenic induced hepatocellular injury, (ii) quercetin, extracted from *Folio uvae ursi* (Bearberry leaves) was chosen as the exogenously supplied antioxidant drug to combat the oxidative stress caused by arsenic induction to hepatic tissue mainly due to its abundant availability in nature and its polyphenolic structure, (iii) the possibility of liposome intercalated drug delivery system was checked for tissue specific or organ specific drug action compared to free drug delivery and (iv) finally, *in vitro* and *ex vivo* stability study of 6-carboxy fluorescein liposomes (% latency) were carried out.

Results and discussion

Liposome encapsulated antioxidants have been tested *in vivo* rat model to prevent oxidative attack during arsenic induced hepatotoxicity. Since hepatic cells are susceptible to reactive oxygen species, protective mechanisms trigger in automatically against oxidative damage. Survival of the hepatic cells depends on equilibrium between free radical generation and counter defense mechanisms¹⁴. During certain conditions like arsenic induced hepatotoxicity, hepatic cells are not able to counter oxidative stress²⁵. Attempts were made to prevent oxidative attack on these cells by introducing antioxidants^{12,13,15}. Endogenous antioxidant therapy is not an effective approach to counter arsenic induced hepatotoxicity. Flavonoids isolated from Indian Medicinal Plants have been proven to show marked antioxidant property when exogenously supplied. Quercetin, extracted from *Folio uvae ursi* (Bearberry leaves) is chosen as the antioxidant drug to combat against the oxidative stress caused by arsenic induction to hepatic tissue mainly due to its abundant availability in nature and its polyphenolic structure.

Liver contains large amount of polyunsaturated fatty acids, which are vulnerable to free radical attack as the double bond within membrane allows easy removal of hydrogen atom by ROS such as OH. The carbon radicals formed in polyunsaturated fatty acids undergo molecular rearrangement to form more stable conjugated dienes, which can crosslink fatty acids within cellular membranes. Oxidative free radical attack on hepatic tissues following arsenic administration in toxic dose was measured by the amount of diene produced per unit tissue proteins, as this parameter is an index of lipid peroxidation.

Results on lipid peroxidation in terms of lipohydroperoxide generation in hepatic tissues of normal and arsenite treated animals are presented in Table 1. A significant increase of lipohydroperoxide ($2.025 \pm 0.030 \mu\text{M}/\text{mg}$ protein) was noted by intra peritoneal (ip) arsenite (12 mg/kg body weight) injection for 5 consecutive days, which is almost 4 times compared to that of the normal un-

Table 1. Determination of lipohydroperoxide in hepatic tissues of normal and arsenite treated animals with and without quercetin

Treatment groups	Diene ($\mu\text{M}/\text{mg}$ protein) ^a
Normal (without arsenite and quercetin treatment)	0.528 ± 0.02
Arsenite treated	2.025 ± 0.03
Arsenite and quercetin treated	1.573 ± 0.04
Arsenite and liposome intercalated quercetin treated	0.643 ± 0.01

^aResults are expressed as mean \pm S.D. of 5 animals.

treated group ($0.528 \pm 0.023 \mu\text{M}/\text{mg}$ protein). Free QC (0.27 mg per 0.5 ml suspension) administration in the dosage regimen of twice a week prior to arsenite treatment resulted in a significant decrease in lipohydroperoxide level ($1.573 \pm 0.038 \mu\text{M}/\text{mg}$ protein) in hepatic cell's. Administration of liposome intercalated QC in the same dosage regimen resulted in a considerably less production of lipohydroperoxide ($0.643 \pm 0.012 \mu\text{M}/\text{mg}$ protein) (Table 1 and Fig. 1A). So, treatment with QC decreased the production of lipohydroperoxide in hepatic tissues, which was further suppressed when QC was introduced in liposome intercalated form. This result clearly suggested that liposome intercalated QC imparted more protection to hepatic tissues than its free form towards arsenite toxicity.

Fig. 1. Effect of quercetin on rat liver tissues : (A) non-treated control group; (B) arsenite treated group; (C) arsenite plus quercetin treated group; (D) arsenite plus liposome intercalated quercetin treated group and (E) latency (%) of hepatic tissues in PBS buffer compared to rat plasma with time. Raw data are presented in Tables 1-5, respectively. Small bars represent the standard deviation of 5 analyses (A-D) or triplicate analyses (E).

The enzymes involved in the primary defense system like superoxide dismutase, catalase etc. play a marked role to combat the free radicals generated in the environment of oxidative stress. The level of generation of these enzymes in liver tissues in the different stress conditions (like arsenite induced or drug induced condition) compared to the normal untreated group is also indicative of the amount of generation of free radicals in the target organs/tissues. When sodium arsenite (12 mg/kg body weight) was introduced to rats, it resulted significant increase of SOD level in hepatic cells (123.39 ± 3.361 units/mg protein) compared to normal untreated one (97.15 ± 5.845 units/mg protein) (Table 2 and Fig. 1B). A little

Table 2. Determination of superoxide dismutase in hepatic tissues of normal and arsenite treated animals with and without quercetin

Treatment groups	SOD (units/mg protein) ^a
Normal (without arsenite and quercetin treatment)	97.69 ± 5.85
Arsenite treated	123.39 ± 3.36
Arsenite and quercetin treated	118.18 ± 1.45
Arsenite and liposome intercalated quercetin treated	106.65 ± 0.95

^aResults are expressed as mean \pm S.D. of 5 animals.

protection was observed in the case of rats pretreated with free QC prior to arsenite treatment as the SOD value

decreased to 118.18 ± 1.45 units/mg protein. On treatment with liposome intercalated quercetin a marked decrease in the SOD value was observed (106.65 ± 0.095 units/mg protein), which was very close to the normal value indicating that free radical generation was considerably decreased by liposome intercalated drug treatment.

In addition, a decrease of catalase value in hepatic cells of the arsenite treated group was observed (36.60 ± 2.89 nM of H_2O_2 reduced/min/mg protein) compared to normal untreated one (63.0 ± 2.82 nM of H_2O_2 reduced/min/mg protein) (Table 3 and Fig. 1C). A little protection was observed in the case of rats pretreated with free QC prior to arsenic treatment as the catalase value in-

Table 3. Determination of catalase in hepatic tissues of normal and arsenite treated animals with and without quercetin

Treatment groups	Catalase (nM of H_2O_2 reduced/min/mg protein) ^a
Normal (without arsenite and quercetin treatment)	63.09 ± 2.82
Arsenite treated	36.60 ± 2.89
Arsenite and quercetin treated	41.99 ± 1.30
Arsenite and liposome intercalated quercetin treated	59.37 ± 4.92

^aResults are expressed as mean \pm S.D. of 5 animals.

creased to 41.99 ± 1.30 nM of H_2O_2 reduced/min/mg protein. On treatment with liposome intercalated QC the catalase value was found to be much near to the normal value (59.37 ± 4.92 nM of H_2O_2 reduced/min/mg protein). In both cases liposome intercalated QC was more effective to control or maintain an environment that protected hepatic tissues from injuries/toxicities due to the production of reactive oxygen species.

Hepatic fibrosis characterized by exuberant synthesis and deposition of collagen in extracellular matrix, which is expressed by the level of collagen deposition as well as the 4-hydroxy proline (4-HP) level. This level was measured when subjected to the different stress conditions and that value was compared to the normal untreated one.

It was seen that the value of 4-HP for normal untreated rat came to 0.2059 ± 0.005 nM per mg protein compared to arsenite treated rat as 0.8513 ± 0.076 nM per mg protein, while on QC treatment its value came to 0.6371 ± 0.018 nM per mg protein. Hence the above result showed that on arsenite treatment the value of 4-HP increased to almost 4 times and on QC treatment the

value decreased a little, which was almost 3 times the normal value. So, sodium arsenite (12 mg/kg body weight) induced appreciably the level of 4-HP (Table 4 and Fig. 1D). Free QC exerted a little on 4-HP level. But on treatment with liposome intercalated QC, the value of 4-HP got almost near to the normal untreated value. It was obvious that the drug when incorporated into liposome (lipid bilayer membrane) showed more optimised action of drug to target tissue i.e. liver than the already existing free drug form.

Table 4. Determination of 4-hydroxy proline level in hepatic tissues of normal and arsenite treated animals with and without quercetin

Treatment groups	4-HP (nM/mg protein) ^a
Normal (without arsenite and quercetin treatment)	0.2059 ± 0.005
Arsenite treated	0.8513 ± 0.076
Arsenite and quercetin treated	0.6371 ± 0.018
Arsenite and liposome intercalated quercetin treated	0.3945 ± 0.01

^aResults are expressed as mean \pm S.D. of 5 animals.

Literature surveys suggested that the efficacy of the liposome formulation was dependant on different physicochemical parameters like membrane fluidity, stability, size, morphology, tissue distribution of the liposome etc.^{16,17}. Among them latency period was studied in this project to estimate its stability. Fig. 1E and Table 5 revealed the stability of liposomes (MLV) prepared from PE : Chol : DCP (7 : 2 : 1 molar ratio) in PBS (pH 7.2)

Table 5. Determination of latency (%) of hepatic tissues in PBS buffer and in rat plasma

Time (h)	Latency (%) in PBS buffer ^a	Latency (%) in rat plasma ^a
0	78.0 ± 1.4	80.0 ± 2.3
1	59.8 ± 2.1	78.8 ± 1.9
2	48.2 ± 1.9	77.2 ± 2.0
3	38.7 ± 2.8	75.4 ± 3.3

^aResults are expressed as mean \pm S.D. of 3 analyses.

and rat plasma. It was observed that liposomes were more stable in PBS than in the plasma. 50% latency of liposomes in PBS and in the plasma required 20.27 and 1.92 h, respectively, which was calculated from the linear regression equation of latency vs time points of incubation

of liposomes in PBS ($Y_1 = -1.54X_1 + 81.7$) and plasma ($Y = -12.95X + 88.55$). Hence, multilamellar liposomes were more stable in PBS (pH 7.2) compared to that in rat plasma as reflected by higher % latency in PBS than that in rat plasma. The decreased stability of these liposomes in plasma was assumed to be due to interaction of liposomes with complement system¹⁷, thus accentuating a faster disruption of the liposomes and release of the entrapped fluorescence dye i.e. 6-carboxy fluorescein.

Experimental

Reagents :

All chemicals were of analytical grade. Ferricytochrome C, cytochrome C, liposome, QC, phosphate, *n*-cyclohexane, superoxide dismutase, xanthine, xanthine oxidase, isopropanol, chloramine-T, Ehrlich's reagent, phosphatidyl-ethanolamine (PE), cholesterol (Chol), dicetyl-phosphate (DCP), 6-carboxy fluorescein (6-CF), 4-hydroxy proline (4-HP), Kpi, EDTA and Triton X-100 were purchased from SD fine Chemicals, Qualigen Chemicals Ltd. and Sigma-Aldrich Chemicals (St. Louis, MO, USA), India. Sodium arsenite from E. Merck, Germany was used for experimental purpose. Quercetin extracted from *Folia uvae ursi* (Bearberry leaves) and was obtained commercially from Extrasynthese S.A. (Genay, France). All reagent solutions were prepared in Milli-Q water.

Instruments :

Fluorescence spectrometer (Perkin-Elmer LS-3), OTD-50B Sorvall ultracentrifuge (Tokyo, Japan), Sorvall SS-34 motor (Tokyo, Japan) and UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Shimadzu, Tokyo, Japan) were used in this study for analyses of samples.

Extraction of quercetin from *Folia uvae ursi* (Bearberry leaves) :

Quercetin was obtained from *Folia uvae ursi* leaves by precipitating the decoction with lead acetate, treating the filtrate with hydrogen sulphide after filtration, again filtering and filtrate was evaporated to the consistence weight of syrup and allowed the product to stand for several days. The syrup gradually assumed the form of a crystalline jelly and the mother liquor was drained off and then pressed to yield nearly colourless crystals which were purified by using solution in boiling water with treatment of animal charcoal. The characterizations of the

extracted and purified QC are discussed in details elsewhere. In the present study ready-made QC was used for all experiments.

Animal experiment design :

Adult male Swiss Albino rats, each weighing approximately 100–120 g, were divided into 4 groups of 5 animals each. Rats in the normal group were injected subcutaneously (SC) with a single dose of physiological saline (0.5 ml). Rats in the control group were injected intraperitoneal with sodium arsenite (12 mg/kg body weight in 0.5 ml physiological saline) for a period of 5 consecutive days. Free drug (0.5 ml suspension contains 0.27 mg QC) and liposome intercalated drug were injected into the tail vein of rats of third and fourth group respectively, following twice a week regimen, 2 h before arsenite treatment, the arsenite treatment being continued for the remaining three consecutive days of the entire week. Animals were anaesthetized; livers were removed, washed with cold physiological saline and kept at -20 °C. All the rats used in this study received proper care in compliance with animal Ethics Committee, India.

Biochemical analysis and enzyme assays :

Lipid peroxidation assay :

Lipids in cyclohexane solvent were assayed at 234 nm and the results were expressed as mM of lipohydroperoxide/mg protein by using a molar extinction co-efficient (ϵ_m) of $2.52 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ^{9,18}. For the determination of conjugated diene one part of the liver was homogenized in 10 ml of phosphate buffer saline (PBS) (pH 7.4) containing 1 mM EDTA. Lipids were extracted from 10 ml of homogenated tissue material using chloroform : methanol mixture (2 : 1, v/v). The extract was evaporated to dryness under nitrogen atmosphere at 25 °C and redissolved in *n*-cyclohexane. Lipids in cyclohexane solvent were assayed at 234 nm and the results were expressed as mM lipohydroperoxide/mg protein by using a ϵ_m of $2.52 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ¹⁹. Proteins were measured as per the method described in Lowry *et al.*¹⁸.

Preparation of cytosolic fraction of liver homogenate :

Liver was homogenized in 0.25 M sucrose with teflon coated homogeniser making 10% homogenate. Then the homogenate was centrifuged at 8200 g for 15 min (Sorvall SS-34 motor, Tokyo, Japan). The supernatant was further centrifuged at 105000 g (35 K) for 60 min at 4 °C

(OTD-50B Sorvall ultracentrifuge). The supernatant from the second centrifugation contained the cytosolic fraction of liver cells leaving pellet as microsomal part.

Superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity :

Superoxide dismutase activity (SOD) in cytosolic fraction of liver homogenate of all the groups of rats was estimated by the method of Beyer and Fridovich²⁰ and was expressed in units by assuming that the activity as one unit which inhibited the initial rate of reduction of ferricytochrome C by 50% in a coupled system with xanthine and xanthine oxidase at pH 7.8 at 25 °C in a 3 ml reaction volume. The concentration of xanthine oxidase should produce an initial (uninhibited) 0.025 ± 0.005 units per min.

Assay utilising cytochrome C and xanthine oxidase :

In this assay, the SOD which competes with the cytochrome C for the flux of $O_2^{\cdot -}$ and 1 unit of SOD is defined as that amount which caused 50% inhibition of the initial rate of reduction of the cytochrome (under the conditions of 50 mM Kpi, 0.1 mM EDTA, 50 μ M xanthine, 10 mM cytochrome, 6 mM xanthine oxidase). It causes absorbance $A = 0.025/\text{min}$ at pH 7.8 and 25 °C in a total reaction volume of 3 ml. The O.D. was measured at 550 nm.

Assay for catalase activity :

2.5 ml H_2O_2 was added to a sample of 2.5 ml and then after 3 min 6 N H_2SO_4 was added. The spectrophotometric reading was taken at 480 nm immediately after addition of 3.5 ml 0.01 N $KMnO_4$. 2.75 ml Phosphate buffer (pH 7) instead of H_2O_2 and sample was taken for the standard sample. Distilled water or phosphate buffer that was used as the sample for the blank with other reagents remained unaltered.

Estimation of hepatic 4-hydroxy proline :

It was determined according to the method of Jammal *et al.*²¹. In brief, the liver was cut into small pieces and homogenised in sufficient deionised water to yield 10% homogenate (w/v). Aliquots (2 ml) of the homogenate were added to an equal volume of 12 N HCl and hydrolysed in Teflon capped vials at 105 °C for 18 h. Aliquots (25 μ L) of individual liver hydrolysates in triplicate were evaporated to complete dryness. The completely dried residue was dissolved in 1.2 ml of 50% isopropanol and

was taken in a test tube. An aliquot (0.2 ml) of 0.56% buffered chloramine-T solution was added to each tube and kept for 10 min at room temperature. The Ehrlich's reagent (1 ml) was added to each tube to give a final volume of 2.4 ml with a calculated chloramine-T concentration of 19.9 mM. All samples were mixed and then incubated at 50 °C for 90 min in a hot water bath. The absorbance was measured at 558 nm using distilled water as reference after blank correction.

Preparation of liposomal quercetin :

Liposomes are prepared by following the method that was described in the literature^{22,23} using phosphatidylethanolamine (PE), cholesterol (Chol), dicetyl-phosphate (DCP) in the molar ratio of 7 : 2 : 1 or simply PE and cholesterol in the molar ratio of 7 : 2. Quercetin was added to the mixture in adequate quantity. The lipids were dissolved in a mixture of chloroform : methanol (2 : 1, v/v) in a round-bottomed flask. The organic solvents were evaporated slowly in an atmosphere of nitrogen to get a lipid film in the wall of the flask. The liposomal suspension was sonicated at 4 °C for 30 s and centrifuged at $1,05,000 \times g$ for 30 min. The pellet was washed and resuspended in PBS to generate multilamellar vesicles (MLV) liposomes. In the optimized conditions it was found that QC intercalated liposomes suspension contained ~ 0.27 mg QC per ml of suspension⁸.

Evaluation of in vitro and ex vivo stability of liposomes using 6-carboxy fluorescein (6-CF) and determination of latency (%) :

The lipid film was prepared as follows. A solution of 6-CF (0.1 mM) was added to the film and allowed to swell for 1 h. After sonication, the liposomal suspension was centrifuged for 30 min at $1,05,000 \times g$. The pellet was washed twice and resuspended in PBS. To assess the stability of liposomes, liposomal suspension (500 μ L) was added either to 3 ml of PBS (pH 7.2) or rat plasma and was incubated for 0 to 3 h. At each time point initial fluorescence (F_0) and final fluorescence (F_t) [after lysing the 6-CF entrapped liposomes with 1% Triton X-100] was measured through fluorescence spectrometer (Perkin-Elmer LS-3) at excitation wave length 490 nm and emission wave length of 520 nm²⁴. The percentage latency was calculated from the formula $[F_t - F_0/F_t] \times 100$ ²².

Latency (%) was plotted against various time points and a straight trend line plot was constructed using MS-Excel Software.

Statistical analysis : All statistical works were done using StatView statistical software (StatView®, SAS Institute Inc., Second Edition, USA, 1998).

Conclusions :

Present studies were designed to elucidate the efficacy of polyphenolic flavonoid quercetin in phospholipid drug delivery system as a cellular and sub-cellular protective drug against liver injury and hepatic fibrogenesis caused by acute exposure of arsenic. Results of the present study suggested that exogenous antioxidant therapy against arsenic induced hepatocellular injury is effective. Quercetin, extracted from *Folia uvae ursi* (Bearberry leaves) is promising to combat against the oxidative stress caused by arsenic induction to hepatic tissue in rats. Liposome intercalated drug delivery system is very effective to combat tissue/organ specific treatment. More research works are necessary on various animal systems as well as humans to accept this drug as a protective drug against hepatomegaly and related disorder after ingestion of arsenic via drinking water, foodstuffs and inhalations.

Acknowledgement

This work has been carried out in Indian Institute of Chemical Biology (Biomembrane Division, IICB, CSIR), Kolkata. The author Anusua Das thanks to Chemistry Division, School of Advanced Sciences, VIT University, Vellore, India for allowing her to do this research work in IICB, Kolkata.

Abbreviations :

Quercetin, QC; Sodium arsenite, NaAsO₂; Reactive oxygen species, ROS; Superoxide dismutase, SOD; Phosphatidyl ethanolamine, PE; Dicyetyl phosphate, DCP; Alkaline phosphatase, AP; High performance liquid chromatography, HPLC; Glutathione peroxidase, GfX; Glutathione, GSH; Glutathione reductase, GR; Glutathione-S-transferase, GST; 4-hydroxy proline, 4-HP.

References

1. NRC (National Research Council), "Arsenic in Drinking Water", National Academy Press, Washington DC, 1999.
2. T. H. Lin, Y. L. Huang and W. C. Tseng, *Bull. Environ. Contain. Toxicol.*, 1995, **54**, 488.
3. S. J. S. Flora, *Clini. Exp. Pharmacol. Physiol.*, 1999, **26**, 865.
4. S. X. Liu, M. Athar, I. Lippai, C. Waldren and T. K. Hei, *PNAS*, 2001, **98**, 1643.
5. N. Mei, N. Kunugita, T. Hirano and H. Kasai, *Biochem. Biophys. Res. Commun.*, 2002, **297**, 924.
6. K. Yamanaka and S. Okada, *Biomed. Res. Trace Elements*, 2000, **11**, 35.
7. S. Ahmad, K. T. Kitchin and W. R. Cullen, *Arch. Biochem. Biophys.*, 2000, **382**, 195.
8. A. K. Mandal and N. Das, *J. Drug Target.*, 2005, **13**, 305.
9. A. K. Mandal, M. K. Basu, R. N. Chakrabarti and N. Das, *JPET*, 2007, **320**, 994.
10. W. Bors, W. Heeller, C. Michel and M. Saran, *Methods Enzymol.*, 1990, **186**, 343.
11. W. Peres, M. J. Tunon, P. S. Collado, S. Herrmann, N. Marroni and J. Gonzalez-Gallego, *J. Hepatol.*, 2000, **33**, 742.
12. B. Havsteen, *Biochem. Pharmacol.*, 1983, **32**, 1141.
13. K. Herrman, *J. Food Technol.*, 1976, **11**, 433.
14. G. J. Cardinal and S. Udenfriend, *Adv. Enzymol.*, 1974, **41**, 2579.
15. J. Wu, G. S. Kuncio and M. A. Zern, in : "Liver growth and repair : from basic Science to clinical practice", eds. A. Strain and A. M. Diehl, Chapman and Hall, London, UK, 1998, pp. 558-576.
16. Shearman, *Br. J. Surg.*, 1996, **83**, 401.
17. M. Yamada, H. Harashima and H. Kiwada, *Biol. Pharm. Bull.*, 1998, **21**, 964.
18. O. H. Lowry, N. J. Rosebrought, A. L. Fan and R. J. Randall, *J. Bio. Chem.*, 1951, **193**, 265.
19. R. O. Recknagel and E. A. Glende, in : "Methods in Enzymology", ed. X. Peacke, Academic Press, New York, 1984, Vol. 105, p. 331.
20. W. F. Beyer, (Jr.) and I. Fridovich, *Anal. Biochem.*, 1987, **161**, 559.
21. I. S. Jammal, V. N. Finelli and S. S. Que Hee, *Anal. Biochem.*, 1981, **112**, 70.
22. G. Gregoriadis, "Liposome Technology", CRC Press, 1884, Vol. 1-3.
23. G. Gregoriadis, *Nature*, 1980, **283**, 814.
24. S. K. Sarin, G. Sharma, S. Banerjee, R. Kathayat and V. Malhotra, *Ind. J. Expt. Biol.*, 1999, **37**, 147.

